

**ROUND TABLE CONFERENCE
ON
CONTEMPORARY ISSUES OF NOMADIC AND
DENOTIFIED TRIBES IN INDIA
ORGANIZED BY
RAJIV GANDHI CENTRE FOR CONTEMPORARY STUDIES,
UNIVERSITY OF MUMBAI & LOKDHARA**

VENUE: SEWAGRAM (WARDHA)

DATE: 4-5 JANUARY 2014

REPORT

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INDEX

SR. NO.	CONTENT	PAGE NO.
1	EXECUTIVE SUMMERY	3-3
2	REPORT OF THE ROUND TABLE CONFERENCE	4-7
3	THE WARDHA DECLARATION	8-9
4	CONCLUSION	10
5	ANNEXURES	
	I: DISCUSSION POINTERS OF GROUP PRESENTATIONS	11-11
	II: PRINT MEDIA COVERAGE	12-14
	II: LIST OF PARTICIPANTS	15-19

Executive Summary

The Rajeev Gandhi Centre for Contemporary Studies, University of Mumbai and 'Lokadhara' jointly organized the two day National level Round Table Conference on Contemporary Issues of Nomadic and De-Notified Tribes at Sewagram, Wardha between January 4 and 5, 2014. Around 200 academicians, activists, researchers, students from all over India actively participated

Prof. Dr. Veena Aalase, Ex-Head, Department of Marathi at Shantiniketan, West Bengal inaugurated the conference. In her speech she focused on the experiences of Mahashweta Devi while working with the indigenous communities and its relevance to the issues of NT-DNT. Mr. Balkrishna Renke, Ex-Chairman National Commission on Nomadic, De-Notified and Semi-Nomadic Tribes, Government of India, expressed his discontent on apathy of Government regarding issues of NT-DNT communities. He raised the concern regarding strategic exclusion of these communities in budgetary provision at Center Government etc.

In his presidential speech, Professor Dr. Chandrakant Puri, Chairperson, Rajeev Gandhi Centre for Contemporary Studies, University of Mumbai, shared his views on political economy of NT-DNT. He stressed on an urgent need of 'Collective Leadership' in DNT movement.

The session was followed by academicians sharing their views on various aspects such as social security, women empowerment, gender, livelihood and legal aspect etc. Dr. Swati Banerjee, Dr. Swaym Panda, Dr. Bal Gurusurthi, Prof. Dr. R. Siva Prasad and Mr. Ganpat Pandit were the panellists. The session followed by sharing of individual experience and the challenges faced at the grassroots level in an open forum.

The First session of second day was started with a group activity. The participants were divided into six groups and were asked to explore different development paradigm of NT-DNT communities. It focused on various perspectives such as social, economic, political and cultural. Human Rights violations and provisions of Renke Commission were two other groups. The group presentation and discussions brought suggestions for the future line of social action for NT-DNT communities. Dr. Bal Gurusurthi invited all the participants for next meeting at Bangalore in February, 2014. The major outcome of the conference was to constitution of National Core Committee and Advisory Committee to take up the issues and concerns of the DNT at the national level. All those who were present at the conference were automatically became members of the NCC and Mr. Balkrishna Renke was selected as its Chairperson and Dr. Bal Gurusurthy as its Secretary for a period of one year.

REPORT OF THE CONFERENCE

DAY-1 – SESSION - I : INAUGURAL SESSION

In her introductory remarks, Adv. Pallavi Renke explained the background of the Round Table Conference for NT and DNT. She raised her concerns regarding 1) the discriminative practices against NT and DNT communities 2) The non-acceptance of recommendations of Renke Commission by the Government and it's reluctant to accept the Renke Commission's report. The need of this RTC was to do a strategic planning to deal with Government's apathy.

Prof. Dr. Veena Aalase inaugurated the conference by garlanding photo frame of Mahatma Gandhi. The conference started with an inspirational song. Mr. Prafull Patil anchored the inaugural session and welcomed all the participants for the session.

Prof. Dr. Veena Aalase, Ex. HOD, Shantiniketan University, West Bengal and awardees' of Sahitya Academy for translation work of Smt. Mahashweta Devi was the Chief Guest for the inaugural session. She spoke on the literature and realities of the society. The stories of Mahashweta Devi were the key anthological experiences for her. She envisioned the issues of marginal population through such writings and reading experiences. She put forth the problems of the NT and DNT

communities in context of globalization. She analyzed the livelihood issues of these communities between their traditions and today's science.

Mr. Balkrishna Renke, Ex-Chairperson, National Commission on NT/DNT, New Delhi delivered the Key Note Address. In his address he explained the politics and the issues of NT and DNT communities. He underlined the negligence and isolation of these communities in development process in the Indian society. He proposed for a separate budgetary provision in five year plan for NT and DNT communities. He demanded that funds and benefits should be allotted as per the proportion of their population. He explained the need of immediate

survey of these populations across the country. The police training laws and its discriminative mis-interpretation against the NT and DNT communities were highlighted by him. He felt that the Government still treats NT and DNT communities as criminal as

per the clause of this law. He suggested a restructuring of the syllabus of police training to avoid such discriminative practice. He demanded immediate access to housing, electricity, livelihood and right to dignity for these communities.

Prof. Dr. Chandrkant Puri, Chair Professor, Rajiv Gandhi Centre for Contemporary Studies, University of Mumbai, in his Presidential speech explained realities of life of NT and DNT communities and the possible strategic intervention in the future. He suggested the model of "Collective Leadership" for the NT-DNT movements. He enforced the need to bring all the small groups, individuals, fractions and NGOs working for the betterment of NT/DNT communities across the country on one platform. He emphasized the need for building political pressure groups and to do advocacy at policy level.

The strategy of sensitization of all political parties for the issues of NT and DNT communities was suggested. He proposed that the success of this RTC will depend on creation of the design for the strong action plan for development of NT/DNTs across India.

DAY-1, SESSION-II : PANEL DISCUSSION :

The topic for the Panel discussion was 'Contemporary Problems of Nomadic and De-notified Tribes in India and Ways forward' wherein the eminent academicians, researchers, field practitioners participated.

Dr. Swyam Panda, Ex-Director-Research, National Commission on NT/DNT, expressed his views on the political perspectives and NT-DNT communities. He strongly put forth the stand on formation of the political party based on the welfare of these communities. He explained the significant transition of Anti Corruption Movement into

the national 'Aam Adami Party' and felt that this is the right time for the community to form its own political party.

Dr. Swati Banerjee, Chairperson Centre for Livelihoods and Social Innovations, TISS, Mumbai, explained the social exclusion of NT and DNT communities in a development paradigm. The continuous alienation of NT and DNT communities from their livelihood resources is a reality. The major discriminative practices are against the women of these communities. She stressed on the need of resolving these problems by establishing their identity with dignity. It will ensure livelihood resources

and eradication of discrimination practices. Social equity, Alternate livelihood resources, Human Rights protection and ensuring inclusion were the four major objectives she focused upon.

Dr. Bal Gurumurthi, Activist and Assistant Professor, National Law School, Bangalore accepted the thoughts expressed by Dr. Panda. In addition, Dr. Gurumurthi expressed the need of National Core Committee which will take political stand for ensuring social justice to these marginal communities. He shared his experiences of working with communities in Karnataka. According to him, the issue of 'Identity Crisis' is the major concern and suggested that the common minimum agenda should be worked out and be resolved in this conference. He emphasized the urgency in designing a cadre building program with the help of the efficient academicians and researchers.

Mr. Ganapat Patil, social activist, MASS, Pune shared his opinion on the issues of NT / DNT. He also proposed the need of political reservation for these communities.

Prof. Dr. R. Siva Prasad analysed the issues of NT/DNT critically and brought attention of participants towards basic needs of the vulnerable people. He emphasized on the study and research of the indigenous people to understand their issues scientifically. He proposed a special innovative education model for the children of NT-DNT communities. He felt that the inter relationship between resources, knowledge and livelihood needs to be explored for their betterment.

Adv. Pallavi Renke in her speech dealt with the legal aspects. She explained with examples, how the draconian laws have negatively affecting the community, which are framed without understanding the socio-cultural background of the NT-DNT Communities. She also felt that the existing laws like Animal Protection Act, the environment act and other such acts are affecting livelihoods of the nomadic and de-notified communities and felt the need to oppose such laws in the court of law.

DAY-1 – SESSION-III : OPEN FORUM.

The third session was based on the experience sharing among the participants across the country. All participants expressed their views and opinions on the social problems of their own community. The suggestions were given by experts / activists to deal with their local problems.

The said Session continued till dinner and generated a lot of discussion on issues concerning NT-DNT.

DAY - 2 : SESSION - I: ISSUES & CHALLENGES OF NT/DNT COMMUNITIES

The sessions for second day of RTC was planned to have group discussions, presentation and resolutions. The first session of the day started with self introduction of participants. It was followed by a group activity. Participants were divided into 6 groups. The themes were classified as Social, Economic, Political, Human Rights/ Legal Rights, Cultural and issues related to Renke Commission Report. The groups were assigned the task to suggest recommendations for overall development of NT-DNT communities. The corresponding presentations were made by the individual group leaders. The academicians and research scholars compiled these suggestions and developed a draft of recommendations.

DAY - 2 : SESSION - II : OPEN SESSION & ADOPTION OF WARDHA DECLARATION

This session was chaired by Mr. Balkrishna Renke. He requested the advisory committee team consisting of academicians to present the draft of resolution for the consent of all participants. Dr. Puri presented all recommendations. Participants clapped to approve each recommendation. There were some rectifications suggested by the participants which were immediately accepted by the team. Mr. Renke appealed to constitute a National Core Committee and an Advisory Committee to address the issues of NT-DNT communities at the National level. Accordingly, the National Core Committee consisting of all those who were present at this conference was formed under the leadership of Shri Balkrishna Renke. Dr. Bal Gurusurthy was appointed as its secretary for one year who will strengthen the NCC, the office of which will be at the NLSIU, Bangalore where he is working at present. All the members present at this RTC were automatically members of the NCC.

The Advisory Committee was constituted to guide the NCC which consisted of Prof. Dr. R. Siva Prasad, Prof. Dr. Chandrakant Puri, Dr. Swayam Panda & Dr. Swati Banerjee. It was proposed by Dr. Bal Gurusurthy to hold the next national level conference at

Bangalore to take forward this agenda and invited all the participants at Bangalore for the national level event which was proposed in February, 2014.

THE WARDHA DECLARATION

1. The Renke Commission Report should be accepted and implemented by the Government of India. While implementing this, following things should be given priority.
2. Identity, Ration-card, Aadhar card, Inclusion in BPL list should be given top priorities.
3. Constitutional safeguards should be provided to NT/DNT.
4. Create employment opportunities / asset for livelihoods.
5. The political, organizational approach plays a vital role in building the national level network and mobilization, therefore it is essential to bring together all prominent leaders of the communities at the national level irrespective of their affiliation to their individual organizations. Same should be done at the state and district level.
6. Budget allocation in proportion to the Population of NT/DNT communities .
7. Priority should be given to Health, Education, Land entitlement, training, skill development etc.
8. Establishment of Permanent NT/DNT Commission.
9. Establishment of NT/DNT National Finance Corporation .
10. Establishment of Land Commission for DNT /NT.
11. Nonprofit Societies establishments on the experience of 'Kallar Reclamation' of Tamilnadu.
12. Issuance of Caste (Tribe) certificates-synonyms names should be taken into account.

13. Adequate Infrastructure for the DNT / NT Communities.
14. Scholarships and free education till graduation.
15. One window system for clearance of projects for DNT/NT.
16. Right to dignity and common properties along with access to livelihood resources.
17. Special budget provision for coaching classes for NT/DNT students.
18. Protect and conserve indigenous knowledge, wisdom and intellectual rights.
19. An Academy should be formed to preserve art, culture of NT/DNT also to develop leadership for NT/DNT.
20. Reservation at all level of political bodied, administration and governance bodies.
21. Prevention of Atrocities Act should be extended to NT/DNTs.
22. Some of the laws which are against the interest of DNT/NT communities be suitably modified.
23. Religious Minorities within the DNT/NT be given priority in development.
24. Creation of Special Micro-financial institutions for promotion of economic sustainability and entrepreneurship.
25. Base Line Survey to study Socio, Economic Status of NT, DNT across India by NSSO.
26. Formation of Core Committee & Advisory Committee to take up issues of NT/DNT.

CONCLUSION:

The Round Table Conference of NT-DNT was A very successful initiative of Rajiv Gandhi Centre for Contemporary Studies, University of Mumbai and Lokadhara. The Academicians, Activists, Researchers and students participated from all over India in this event. The National Core Committee and Advisory Committee were approved in the gathering. The need of political pressure group was emphasized. The strategic intervention policy was designed for ensuring the fundamental constitutional rights of NT-DNT communities. The collective leadership was the outcome of this Round Table Conference. It resulted into “**Wardha Declaration**” consisting of 26 Demands for the development of NT-DNT Communities.

Annexure -I: NT-DNT Discourses in Group Discussion

Issues
Social Discrimination/Atrocities
Wild Life Protection Act
Anti-Beggary Act
Drug and Medicinal Act
Habitual Offenders Act
Laws Amendments
Cooperative Societies without political party interest
Petition on Local and regional issues to local/district/state/central govt. authorities
Legal Definition of "Minorities"

NT, DNT
DISCOURSES

Do's
Act Extent to NT, DNT communities across all states
Caste Certificate and BPL Lists
Amendments
Amendments
Amendments
Dignity for NT, DNT
Funding, Education Infrastructure, Entrepreneurship, Subsidies
Common programs all over India
Caste wise Definition

Suggestions
Two committees 1. Anthropologists 2. Activists
Campaign for Common Identity as "Nomad" across India
Most vulnerable should priorities first for core group formation
Livelihood Assets creation and house facilities providers campaign across India
Campaign for validation of Identity proof with an authority to the local NT, DNT organizations
Designing of training programmes and sensitization camps for cadres empowerment and capacity building
Establishment of an independent NT, DNT commission at center level with state level commissions
Advocacy for discussion and acceptance of recommendations of Renke commission report in parliament
Govt. land reform with identification of "Govt. land" and distribution of resources
Creation of redress mechanism and grievance Cell at state level
Creation of Special Micro-financial institutions for promotion of economic sustainability
Sensitization campaigns for executives
Base Line Survey: Socio, Economic Status of NT, DNT
Political awareness campaign for 'Karykarta' at village and block level
Establishment of National level core committee for the giving appropriate direction to the grass root level's Organizations

Development Perspectives :

- A] Social
- B] Economic
- C] Political
- D] Cultural
- E] Human Rights
- F] Legal Rights
- G] Renke Commission Report

ANNEXURE-II: PRINT MEDIA COVERAGE

ANNEXURE III : LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

Though around 200 participants attended the event, the registration process was stopped as the inaugural programme was started. This list is only of those who formally registered at the event.

Sr. No.	Name of the Participant	Organization/Address	Mobile No.
1	Dagduba Ramkishan Chindhote	Member, Kevat Samaj Mahasangh, Maharashtra, A/P Kumbharsari, Block- Jalabad, Dist- Jalana- 431208	9552719460
2	Pratap Manikrao Mane- Patil	Principal, AshramSchool Mardi, Block- Lohara, Dist- Osmanabad. (Rajiv Gandhi Chowk, Shahupuru Coloney, Latur)	9421370122
3	Shankar Apparao Bhise	Bhise Chawl, Sane Guruji Nagar, Asasna, Ghatkopar, Mumabi (W)	9869115413
4	Raju Bhise	Yuva, Yuva Centre, Plot No. 23, Sector-7, Kharghar, Navi Mumbai	9960464430
5	Bharat kale	Yuva, Yuva Centre, Plot No. 23, Sector-7, Kharghar, Navi Mumbai	9867284448
6	Ms. Swati Jadhav	C-504, Radhika Hausing Society, Sinhgad Road, Pune-30	9423593536
7	Swayam Panda	A-1801, Samrpan, Western Express way, Borivali (E)	845404211
8	Dr. Balaguru Murthy	President, Karnataka Nomads Mahasabha, Bangalore	9341341124
9	Dr. R Siva Prasad	Professor/Head, Dept. of Anthropology, University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad- 500046	9848497665
10	Deekonda Narsingarao	Sadbawana, H No. 4-1-114, VST coloney, Tarnaka, post- Nacharam, Secunderabad- 500076	09849552877, 09849508565
11	Ramesh Sakharam Kevat	Secretary, Kevat Samaj Mahasangh, Maharashtra, A/P Andhera, Block- Deoolgaonraja, Dist- Buldhana-443201	0960469351, 09049173485
12	Ms. Yogini Dolke	Srujan, 49, Shankarnagar, Nagpur-10	9326585234
13	Sudhakar Badgujar	Chatra Yuva Sangharsh Vahini, A/P Panache Kurhe, Block- Bhusawal, Dist- Jalgaon	7588053319
14	Rambhau Tryambakrao Gaikawad	Renuka Gondhali Samaj, Chalisgaon, Jalgaon	9822396353, 9730382039
15	Krishnarao Vishwnath Jadhav	Nashik Jilha Renuka Gondhali Samaj Multipurpose Organization, Nashik, 68- Saiprasad, Ashapur Hou. So. Dhattrak Phata, Panchvati, Nashik- 422003	9923136652
16	Prakash Rambhau Ogale	Treasurer, Nashik Jilha Renuka Gondhali Samaj Multipurpose Organization, Nashik, Sham Hightes, Flat No.-3, Vrundavan Coloney, Navin Nashik, Khodemala-9	9970079047

17	Ganpat Baburao Pankar	A/P Nagothane, Block- Roha, Dist- Raigarh	8796636683
18	Ms. Kalpan Santosh Patil	Mahila Sanghatan, A/P Nagothane, Block- Roha, Dist- Raigarh	9270734960
19	Shivaji Appa Bhise	Bhataka Vimukta Sangh, Moreshwar Chawl, Maharashtra Nagar, Mankhurd, Mumbai-88	9833874646
20	Ganpat Shantaram Pandit	MAAS, 201, Akanksha Residency, Near Shivaji Statue, Aundhgaon, Pune-007	9423583637
21	Abhijit Prakash Bhalerao	MAAS, 201, Akanksha Residency, Near Shivaji Statue, Aundhgaon, Pune-007	9921604232
22	Ms. Lata Pratibha Madhukar	TISS and CSD Research Scholor, C/O CSD, 5-6-151, Near NIRD Gate, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad-500030	09666957988, 09922320338
23	N T Durai Singam	16-1-144, A David Compound, Keelapudur, Urilampatti, Madurai, Tamilnadu	9786547787
24	Dr. Anand Kakade	A-13, sbi Coloney, Ujwal Nagar, Samalwad, Nagpur-440025	8007321475, 9960100633
25	Nitin Vinayakrao Gosavi	President, Maharashtra Bhatkya Vimukta Vikas Sanstha, Nandurbar	8484942403
26	Jitendra Madhavrao Parmar	Maharashtra Bhatkya Vimukta Vikas Sanstha, Nandurbar	9423942556
27	Dr. Prashant Sadashiv Bhosale	Asst. Professor, Social Work College, Jalgaon	9766779700
28	Dharmveer Chavhan	Go. Jo. Buva Sanghatana, STRT 17/1, Cross Road 16, ABL Coloney, Shahabad, Gulbarga, Karnataka	9449766555
29	Anantrao (Antu) B Bharaut	B-401, Sanskriti Building, Anand nagar, Dahisar (E)	9869504799, 09811172031
30	Mahendra Vakode	108, Telagi Paccha Peth, Jagdamba nagar, Solapur	9890469890
31	Pradnyesh (Appa) Parshuram Vakode	Horizon Hight, 102, First floor, Near RTO, Lokhandwala, Andheri (W) Mumabi	9327262495, 9892585653
32	Nitin Pandit Bhoi	PJN College of Social Work, Amalner, Dist- Jalgaon	9657870355, 9823422859
33	Kishor Bhaskar Mali	PJN College of Social Work, Amalner, Dist- Jalgaon	9158255622
34	K Surendran	Advocate, 14, Besant Road, Chokkikulan, Madurai-2, Tamilnadu	9443734352
35	Vilas Bhongade	Kashtkari Jan Andolan, Vanrainagar, Manewada, Nagpur-440034	9890336873
36	Sevak Shilikram Bashi	Nagpur	9860248292
37	Nishant Mate	Asst. Professor, Social Work College, Kamptee, Nagpur	9423407433
38	Pravin Mote	Nagpur	9373928263
39	Jaideep Hardikar	Nagpur	

40	Rajendra N Bathiye	G/4 Vitthal Rukmini Mandir, Geeta Nagar, Nagpur-30	9970070405
41	Milind N Sonune	Nagpur	9421777372
42	Ms.Vaishali Milind Sonune	Nagpur	9404082810
43	Ashoka M Vaidu	Shahada, Nadurbar	9423222609
44	Vaiki Vedu vaidu	Shahada, Nadurbar	7875193566
45	Dr. K M Metry	Professor, Dept. of Tribal Studies, Kannada University Hampi-583276	9448632685
46	Dr. Jakka Parthsarthy	Visiting Professor, Dept. of Tribal Studies, Kannada University Hampi-583276	9443257638
47	Siddhu Thorvat	State Coordinator, (DNts Study) Dept. of Tribal Studies, Kannada University Hampi-583276	9740230309
48	Narendra Gangadhar Vandre	D-2/4, Anupamnagar, Murbad Road, Kalyan (W) Dist-Thane	9967458611
49	Prof. Vandre Shantaram Jagannath	Prsident, Otari Samaj, Sheikh Chawl, Near Bharat Coloney, Kamalghar, Bhiwandi-421302	9922243371
50	D Girish	Devalapur Hospet, Bellary, Karnataka	8970029643
51	Ms. Sandhya R Krishnan	Senior Programme Officer, SwissAidIndia, Pune	9405616941
52	Ms. Veena Alase	Shanti Niketan, West Bengal	
53	Dr. Pancham Rajbhar	Ex. General Secretary, Akhil Bharti Rajbhar Sanghathan, UP	8009409770
54	K Gopi	Hyderabad, AP	9391008916
55	Sardarsinh Vagari	Hatnara, Post- Malbasa, Ratlam, MP	9827250803
56	Channu ram Bawaria	State President Haryana, All India Samasth Bawaria Samaj Sanghathan, Ex. Advisor, DNT Commission (India)	8053909115
57	Jagan Dhuvallal Goraman	Mukeshnagar, Nagpur	9923119671
58	N S Pawar	A/P Dhamori (Kasaba), Block- Bhatkuli, Dist- Amrawati	8055407970
59	Bharat Veetkar	Rajlok Niwas, Survey No.-56, Suryprakash Nagar, Kharadi, Pune-14	9881902287, 9850119922
60	Dr. J P Baghel	D-204, Pleasant Park, Near Dahisar Bridge, Dahisar (W) Mumbai- 400068	9869078485
61	Ramdas R Bhand	18, Vrindawan Coloney, Silani Stop, Jail Road Nashik-42210	9881556226
62	Prabhakar B Mandhare	Plot No.- 17, Reshimbaug, Nagpur-440009	9822577910, 0712- 2746932
63	Bhanudas Satawji Pawar	Ward No.- 6, Shivaji Nagar, Mehkar, Dist-Buldhana-443301	99222680782

64	Sanjay Rupravaji Solanke	Akola Road, Near Vidyut Bhavan, Banosa, Block-daryapur, Dist- Amravati	9763270557
65	Apparam Parmar Chandrvanshi	Bharala, Post- Rupera, Block- Nagada, Dist- Ujjen, MP-4456335	9754139265
66	Dharmpal Premlal Shende	17, Suabhagya Nagar, Ward No. 1, Hulkeshwar Road, Nagpur- 440034	9011018964
67	Annaji Raut	Ex Deputy Mayor, Municipal Corporation, Nagpur, Sambhaji Kasar Road, Mehandibaug Road, Taraipura, Nagpur	9850354504
68	Dr. Vasudeo Dahake	201, Kabeer Palace, Zingabai Takali, Om Nagar, Koradi Road, Nagpur-440030	9422823705
69	Satish Marotrao Navarkhele	Quarter No.- 291, New Mhada Coloney, Arvi Road Wardha- 442001	9372911016
70	Bhavarlal Bhival Geet	Bharala, Post- Rupera, Block- Nagada, Dist- Ujjen, MP-4456335	7354781029
71	Nemsing Baghel	Coordinator, Gujrat Pal Maha Samaj, Baroda	9427343302
72	Nareshkumar Patil	C/O Shamrao Navrage Masala, Wardha	9527160485
73	Dr. Pranali Patil	College of Social Work Kamptee, Nagpur	9766017785
74	Purushottam D Bhoyar	19, Vrindavan Coloney, Katol Road, Nagpur	9579277043
75	Rahul H Khadse	Viakas Sahyog Pratishthan, Mumbai	
76	Ashok D Satpute	Kumbhalkar College of Social Work, Wardha	7588935303
77	Sarthak Banerjee Puri	B-204, Daffodills, Mumbai	9773710790
78	Sundarlal	A/P Dhapri, Block- Selod	9421726894
79	Pande Maharaj	A/P I'ali, Block- Selod	9422142574
80	Babasaheb Galat	Krishnanagar, Arvi	
81	Uddhav Gadekar	Secretary, Gavali Samaj Sanghathan, Vighnharta nagar, Near Post Office, Wardha	9975323462
82	Sitaram Nagorav Shende	Working President, Vaidarbhiy Gadi Lohar va Tatsam Jati Mahasangh, Opposite to Dr. Tumbade Hospital, Balaji Ward, Bastarpur, dist- Chadndrapur	9860423131
83	Vilasrao Kusale	A/P Gadchandur, Chandrapur	7798833930
84	Anandrao Y Angalwar	President, Maharashtra VJNT Ekata Sangh	9403320507
85	Ms. Prabhatai B Chilake	Adivisor, Maharashtra VJNT Ekata Sangh	
86	Rumindas Bhosale	President, Adivasi Parivar, Wardha	9923510106
87	Dr. Swati Banerjee	TISS, Mumabi	
88	D B Nat	Shrikrishna Gavali, Chandrapur	
89	D N Waghmare	Sangharsh, Nagpur	9370772752

90	Mukund B Adevar	Vimukt Bhatakanti Samaj, 129, Kukadi, Nagpur	9822120161
91	Deepak C Raibhar	Vimukt Jati, Aroli, Mumbai	9819601595
92	C W Meshram	11, New Garden, Viman Nagar, Pune	
93	Anil Amzare	District Secretary, Vidharbh Bhoi Samaj Sanghatana, Wardha	9421931656
94	Yeshwant	Wardha	
95	Pappu Dashrathji Sawant		9764476351
96	Ms. Vidya rajendra Kalsait	Member, Village Panchayat Pipari Meghe, Wardha	9921678784
97	Rajendra Kalsait	Behind Rashtriy Samajik Vidyalay, Arvi Road, Wardha	9881332162
98	Nandkishor Ukandrao Raut	Shriram Kala Mahila Mahavidyalay, Dhamangaon Relway, Amrawati	9970886531, 9604512168
99	Dattatray Thakare	Social Worker, Khamgaon, Buldhana	9970779007
100	Bhaulal Sanise Babar	Jalgaon-Jamod, Buldhana	9922013717
101	Narayan K Shinde	Satyamnagar Layout, Yavatmal	7776913003
102	R S Pathanekar	Mahendra Coloney, Amrawati	9326289227
103	Deekonda Suresh	H No. 12-13-711, Tarnaka, Hyderabad-500017	9908938935
104	Ms. Seema Deshmukh	Muskan, Bhopal	9827302869
105	Ms. Savita	Muskan, Bhopal	
106	Sadashiv Hirlekar	18, Janata Hou. Soc. Dindayal Nagar, Nagpur-22	9422843743
107	Dharmendra N Batho	Nishadraj Jalvanghi Samaj, nagpur	9595209272
108	Vijay Rama Padhari	A/P Dongargaon, Akola-444104	9850058658
109	Suresh Rama Padhari	A/P Dongargaon, Akola-444104	9850058658
110	Mallu Durg Pawar	A/P Janwa, Block- Amalner, Dist- Jalgaon	
111	Ambaram Parmar	Bharala, Post- Rupera, Block- Nagada, Dist- Ujjen, MP-4456335	9754139265
112	Sanjay Manikrao Panchpatre	Near Masjid, Pravin Nagar, Amravati-444006	9403170210
113	Dr. Chandrakant Puri	Mumbai University	9819056444
114	Shri Balkrishna Renke	Solapur	9422457471
115	Mrs. B. Renke	Solapur	9422457172
116	Adv. Pallavi Renke	Solapur	9422457170
117	Dr. Swayam Panda	Mumbai	8454042111